

THE FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF CARBON FIBRE
REINFORCED Pb-Sn COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The experimental work which has led to our present understanding of the fracture of carbon fibre reinforced Pb-10%Sn composite is reviewed. A dynamic observation of the fracture process is carried out under SEM. It is found that there are two kinds of fracture mechanisms existing in Pb-Sn composite, i.e., the failure of the composite dominated by the breaking of fibres and by the premature fracture of matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Most of prevailing theories about longitudinal tensile fracture behavior of composite materials with continuous fibre are based on the condition that fibers break prior to nucleation of matrix cracks under the applied load [1-3]. Therefore, the fracture of composite is regarded as being dominated by the breaking of fiber. But, this assumption does not fit all situations. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the fracture mechanism of metal matrix through the observation of the fracture process of Pb-Sn composite.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

Pb-10%Sn alloy has been selected as matrix material. The composite is fabricated by liquid infiltration method and the carbon fibre content is 15 percent volume fraction of the composite. Before incorporating with Pb-Sn matrix, the surface of carbon fibre is covered with an uniform

nickle layer by chemical-plating process.

The test specimen is straightly sided with a demension of 64x5x0.5mm.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The dynamic observation of the fracture process of Pb-Sn composite is taken under SEM with a crosshead speed of 0.001mm/min. During the tensile process, the specimen is loaded in a direction parallel to the filaments and strictly aligned to minimize bending stresses.

The fresh fracture surfaces of Pb-Sn composite are observed under SEM after the tensile test above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 1, if the distribution of carbon fibre in matrix is uniform and the spacing between fibres is wide enough, the fracture mechanism of Pb-Sn composite can be approximately illustrated by Rosen's cumulative weakening model. Assuming the strength of the carbon fibre obeys Weibull's distribution function [5], some fibres with low strength are broken at a certain stress level (Fig. 1a) and no cracks are formed in matrix. But in the region ahead of crack tip, the stress concentration is induced and a nonuniform Shear stress field is built up along the interface of the fibre and the matrix, simultaneously. As the load increases, the magnitude of the stress concentration is severely raised, which results in plastic deformation of the matrix and in turn stress relaxation of the stress concentration region. Thus, the crack tip is blunted by the plastic deformation of the matrix and the crack is unable to propagate into the matrix (Fig. 1b). At the same time, many microvoids begin to nucleate at the second phase particales Ni_3P and Ni_3Sn in the original nickle layer by interfâcial separation. With further strain, these microvoids gradually grow, coarsen and interact with each other and finally connect to form a crack, i.e., the original crack produced due to broken fiber begin to propagate into the matrix. Near the broken ends of the fibre where the shear stress attains the maximum the interfâcial debonding of fibre and matrix begin to oxxur [6]. But the interfâcial debonding is not a continuous process. This is because the shear stress rapidly decrease as the interfâcial debonding proceeds, next debonding process does not occur unless the shear stress is accumulated to high level again. So, the whole

a.

b.

c.

d.

Figure 1. The common fracture process of Pb-10%Sn composite material interfacial debonding process is an intermittent process, which can be demonstrated by the evidence of the circular slip bands on the wall of the hole along the axile of the fiber (Fig. 2). When the stress is over the average strength of fibre, most of the carbon fibres join in breaking.

This results in a cumulative weakening section of the specimen. In this section all of the cracks propagate at a high speed. And in the region adjacent to the dangerous section the fracture of broken ends of the fibre propagate into this weakest section through the interfacial debonding. After all of the fibres have broken, the fibres are drawn out from the matrix and finally the matrix is separated into two parts. From the fractograph of Pb-Sn composite (Fig. 3), we find that the length of the fibre drawn out from the matrix is adequate. On the matrix there are a lot of dimples and the apparent tearing ridges covering the whole surface. These coincide with the analysis of the fracture process of Pb-Sn composite above. This kind of fracture mechanism of Pb-Sn composite ensures the function of transferring applied load of matrix, the high strength of the fibre can be brought in to full play, and the tensile strength of Pb-Sn composite can be evaluated by ROM law.

Figure 2. The fracture surface of Pb-Sn composite: there are a lot of dimples and the apparent tearing ridges existed on the matrix surface. On the wall of the hole, some circular slip bands are found along the axile of fibre.

Figure 3. The fracture surface of Pb-Sn composite with high fibre content, the tearing ridges are low and narrow.

In the case of the segregation of the fibre in matrix or the high content of the fibre, the fracture mechanism of Pb-Sn composite will change (Fig. 2). From Fig. 4a, we find that the spacing between the fibres is narrow, there are no fibres to break except one broken fibre due to specimen preparation. As loaded, the cracks initiate in the matrix between the fibres without the breaking of the fibre (Fig. 4b). This phenomenon

can be explained by the following two reasons: 1. the matrix between the fibers is embrittled due to the plastic constraints [1, 4]. 2. the matrix between fibres mainly consists of plated nickle layer. Figure 3 shows that the tearing ridge is low and narrow. This is because the microvoids form at low stress early and coarsen with great ease. With further increase of the

a.

b.

c.

d.

e.

Figure 4. The fracture process of Pb-Sn composite with the segregation of carbon fibre in matrix or high carbon fibre content.

load, the cracks formed in many sites along the axle of the fibre rapidly propagate in three directions (Fig. 4c, d). Soon the matrix breaks to pieces and cannot transfer the load to the fiber (Fig. 4c). Since this results in that the high strength of the fibre can not be brought into play, the tensile strength of the composite is certainly lower than ROM value. This fracture mechanism of Pb-Sn composite is similar to that of composite with brittle matrix [7].

According to the above discussion, the following conclusions are derived.

1. Two kinds of fracture mechanisms of Pb-Sn composite are found, the different fracture mechanisms determine the tensile strength of Pb-Sn composite.

2. In order to ensure that the composite fractures as the fracture mechanism of fibre dominant properties, the uniform distribution of fibre in matrix, adequate fibre content of composite and the matrix with good toughness are required.

3. The interfacial debonding of fibre and matrix is an intermittent process.

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